

Development of load shedding web-based monitoring and control system

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Abstract

Electricity as an essential part of modern life has in recent times experienced a surge whereas the quantity generated and transmitted is quite lower than the consumption rate. This calls for load shedding to manage the available power. This research, therefore, develops a web-based load monitoring and control system which allows users to perform load shedding remotely via a web server. This work unlike previous works gives a load profile of various appliances within a household in order to know the appliances consuming more energy than others to manage the use of such to conserve energy. The hardware components include sensors and NodeMCU microcontroller that are interfaced with web applications. The test results indicate that the device can remotely monitor the energy consumption of each of the connected appliances in real-time on a mobile phone or web interface where load-shedding is implemented. When the developed system is integrated with a smart meter, it has the potential of providing information to consumers about their power usage and enabling them to make an informed decision (load shedding) that would reduce their electricity bills.

Keywords: Load Shedding, Monitoring and Control, Smart Meter, Energy Consumption

1. Introduction

The growing population, improved economic activities, and increased investments have all pushed up the demand for electricity consumption [1]. The rise in demand for electricity in Nigeria over the last decade has been fueled by a rapid increase in the country's annual residential development, which has played a significant role in increasing the demand for electricity. There's the need to build new power-producing units to meet the predicted need for electrical power to comply with development plans, population growth, and rising living standards. When compared to the high cost of constructing new generating power units, a load management system would be an appealing resource that should be seriously regarded as an important part of the national energy programme, especially in situations where the demand rate exceeds supply. According to [2], electricity outage is the main challenge confronting the residential, commercial, and industrial sectors in Nigeria.

Load management is the process of scheduling loads to reduce electric energy consumption. It is optimizing processes or loads to improve the system load factor. Several methods of load management can be followed by an industry or utility company. One major method is load shedding which is the process of taking off excess load from systems to maintain the stability of the power system [3]. Other methods include load shifting, installing energy-efficient processes, energy storage devices, and co-generation to mention a few. Load shedding is aimed at distributing the available power to consumers by turning off one

area for another area to be supplied power thereby serving all consumers by reducing brownouts [1].

2. Related Work

In recent times, there has been a significant amount of scholarly research on load management techniques that are managed and monitored using particular devices. Following a review of the studies conducted by various individuals and groups, it was discovered that only a few studies pointed in the direction of user comfortability and better real-timed switching on the system. Some related works are discussed below:

The authors in [4] developed a teaching and research module for automatic load shedding using an Arduino microcontroller in which a power distribution was proposed. An assumed state of 7.5 MW maximum out of the 10 MW power required for proposed cities was available. As a result, there was a need for load shedding. The cities to be managed were grouped into four divisions namely: residential, industrial, commercial, and University Teaching Hospital (UTH). The simulation results showed an effective automatic load shedding mechanism between the residential, commercial, and industrial regions thereby eliminating the need for distribution companies to manually engage staff for that purpose but did not incorporate remote and real-time power monitoring and control capabilities. The implementation of a load control system using GSM Technology by [5], where a remote user sends commands to the receiver through an android application that has been set up to handshake with the remote system developed. The proposed system could operate and monitor nearly all electrical appliances

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from the comfort of an android smartphone application which gives users comfort and effective power management. According to [6], the implementation of a control system based on an automated load-shedding controller reduced manual effort in systematically controlling the load-shedding time interval. This technology also warns users before doing partial or full load shedding; results showed that the system saves energy as well as distributes power through different set-out criteria.

In [7], the authors presented a review of techniques for load shedding where the research focuses on the review of the load-shedding techniques, control algorithms, simulation platforms and integrations, and control devices used for the DC microgrid. The analyses reported in the paper upheld the importance of the distributed multi-agent system (MAS) in implementing distinct control operations including load-shedding.

The study investigated the issues of building and executing intelligent load-shedding techniques using microgrid systems but there is a need to engage in further research to determine the influence of communication on the reliability of load-shedding systems. The development of an intelligent micro-grid scheme by [8], with a soft touch human-machine interface for the remote monitoring and control of the hybrid power pool system with load shedding capability for energy sustainability was another innovation. The results reveal that the system is triggered irrespective of the location of use and the system can monitor usage and also change any supply preferences needed.

The authors in [9] considered an efficient power use model achieved through automatic control of loads using a mobile app and a Bluetooth module which could solve the problem of power wastage in developing countries where hydroelectric power is not easily accessible by developing a load shedding system controlled by a mobile application [10] developed a load shedding notification system which uses an android-based load shedding and notification mechanism. The work comprises two sections: first, which deals with the selection of primary and secondary lines while the second manages the load shedding and notification process. The primary power line is connected to the load line as long as the voltage level is in the threshold range which is selected as 225 to 235 in this work. Otherwise, the relay connects the secondary power line with the load line. Arduino-based LCD shows the voltage of the primary power line while the status of load shedding is monitored by Node MCU and according to the type of load shedding it either switches on or off output load. This work designed a computerized Load Shedding Controller (LSC) to reduce the manual effort for controlling the load shedding time interval systematically.

The works of [11] presented the basic perception and methodology of modern intelligent load shedding schemes in microgrids topology by employing TCP/IP protocol for fast and intelligent switching. The network understudy performs load management and power distribution intelligently in a unified network. The generated power is efficiently distributed among local loads through a fast communication system of servers in the form of source and clients in the form of loads through TCP/IP. The efficient use of information between server and clients enables astute control of the load shedding in a power system of microgrids system. The work of Benjamin [12] developed a **load shedding system** to match load with available supply using an automated system IoT. The **work relied on IoT - based within a** Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system in which smart meters deployed at the consumer's end communicate with the Master SCADA for ON/OFF signals.

There is now an increasing awareness that an electricity consumer (customer) needs to have basic information about his electricity consumption to take an informed decision about the rate of usage thereby saving cost. This is achieved by the incorporation of meter-to-consumer communication into the metering system. With the use of analog meters, the consumer is only aware of his consumption at the end of the month when he receives the electricity bill. With digital meters, a consumer can check the consumption or balance from time to time using the information provided on the digital meter but is not aware of which of the devices is consuming more electricity and which one is consuming less. Whereas this piece of information if known could assist him to determine the extent of use of such an appliance through load shedding to reduce his electricity bills.

This concept of load-shedding can also be used in the power distribution set-up in residential or industrial buildings [4]. Customers are encouraged to shut down the lights they are not using at particular times to prevent their electricity meters from working round the clock resulting in high electricity bills. The process of effectively determining the power consumption of an individual is referred to as metering. Different meter types are used for this process including analog meters and digital meters. The recent types of digital meters are referred to as smart meters. With the advancement in metering systems, electricity consumers do not need to rely solely on utility companies for information about their electricity consumption. The customer or consumer using appropriate technologies can send and receive information from their electricity smart meters. This communication may include retrieval of electricity bills, crediting of electricity accounts, and remote control of appliances to mention a few [13 - 16]. In many of these cases, a consumer sees the total consumption but is not aware of the details of what is being consumed by each of the appliances on his premises. The proposed system is unique in the sense that it will provide on-the-go information about the power consumption of different household appliances in a digital and graphical format so that the consumer can plan the use of electricity for such appliances. The user will be able to shut down (load-shed) appliances using menus on his mobile phone from remote locations to reduce consumption thereby managing his power consumption economically and sustainably. The rest of the work is arranged in this way. Section 2 is the methodology, section 3 the results and the discussion of results and conclusion are found in sections 4 and 5 respectively.

3. Research Methodology

The developed system will be discussed in three sections namely: the hardware, the connection to the web application, and the software section.

3.1 Hardware

The system architecture consisting of major hardware components is shown in Fig. 1 while Fig. 2 shows the circuit representation. The microcontroller known as the NodeMCU is the brain of the device. It controls the relays A and B based on the data being fed into it from the alternating current (AC) sensor which is used to measure the power of the appliances under consideration. This enables the shedding of the load through the actuators. The sensor used in this work is a PZEM-004T V3 Sensor. This sensor can measure several parameters including AC voltage, Current, active energy, active power, frequency power factor among others

Fig. 1: Architecture of the hardware module

Fig. 2: Circuit diagram of the hardware module

3.2 Connection to the Web application

The NodeMCU microcontroller has Wi-Fi capability with which it connects to the web server/database and then to the web interface on his mobile phone. This illustration is shown in the system architecture of Fig. 1. The network employed in this work is a Local Area Network (LAN) while the web server is hosted on a personal computer with Xamp as a local host. The components in the hardware work together to obtain measured data such as AC voltage, current, active power, frequency, power factor, and active energy. The measured values from the PZEM-004T V3 Sensor are received by the microcontroller and repeatedly sent to a database using the API written in PHP. The Hardware module communicates with the software over a mobile hotspot device. On connecting the hardware to the network, it receives a unique internet protocol (IP) address. The assigned IP address identifies it uniquely on the network. The flow of data between the hardware and MySQL database is represented in Fig. 3 indicating the relationship between the PHP

API (software), the microcontroller (hardware), and the database (software).

Fig. 3: Connection from the microcontroller to the database

3.3 Software Section

The software part of the system is divided into the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) and the Web Application. The Arduino (IDE) is made up of a text editor which is used for writing codes, a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions, and a series of menus. The algorithm to operate the device is coded in embedded C language and uploaded into the microcontroller. The flowchart for this algorithm is shown in the flowchart of Fig. 4. Once the device is switched on, the system initializes by ensuring connection to hardware, software, and network. After these measured values from the sensor are read by the microcontroller, it sends the same to the webserver/database through the API. From the webserver, the actuators are energized to on or off appliances and measured sensor values are displayed on the web interface. The user can also take a reverse direction from the web interface to send actuating signals to the microcontroller via the web server and network. The Web Interface was designed with a combination of Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML), Cascaded style sheet (CSS), JavaScript, jQuery, and PHP. The system hardware and software were incorporated together and packaged. The system prototype is shown in Fig. 5 displaying hardware components with their interconnections.

Fig. 4: Flowchart of proposed system

Fig. 5: Interconnection of system components

4.0 Results and Discussion

The developed system has different features including a web interface, database, and appliances connection or interface unit. From the web interface dashboard as shown in Fig. 6, the user can view in real-time the graphical form of the measured parameters from different appliances in terms of current, voltage, power, energy, power factor, and frequency. Another feature at the lower part of the web interface is the control panel. The control panel is labeled load A, load B, and load C indicating different appliances. From the control panel in Fig. 6, load A is unchecked while loads B and C are checked. Unchecking load A for example turns off the appliance associated with it while checking loads B and C turns on the associated appliances. By following this procedure, users have the opportunity to monitor their loads (appliances) and perform load-shedding wirelessly from remote locations over the network as they deem fit. The web interface can be accessed using a mobile phone or a personal computer. Fig. 7 is MySQL database for storing measured values of the appliances.

Fig. 6: Web interface for monitoring and control of appliances

Fig. 7: MySQL database for storing measured parameters of appliances

The developed load-shedding device was connected to different household appliances and tests were carried out to evaluate the performance of the system. The appliances include resistive load (5 W energy saving bulb), resistive Loads (5 W Energy Saving and 60 W incandescent bulbs), resistive and inductive loads (5 W energy saving bulb, 60 W incandescent bulb, and 50 W standing fan) as shown in Fig. 8 a - c.

Fig. 8: Testing the device with a) resistive load (5 W energy saving bulb) b) resistive Loads (5 W Energy Saving and 60 W incandescent bulbs) c) resistive and inductive loads (5 W energy saving bulb, 60 W incandescent bulb, and 50 W fan).

Tests were carried out by using the mobile phone to remotely switch on the appliances at a distance of 4 m over a Wi-Fi network while observing how the values displayed when different appliances were turned on. Table 1 indicates the readings from the test and the results for this test which are also indicated through graphs and the web interface. Fig. 8a, the appliances connected and switched on include a mobile phone, 60 W incandescent bulb, and a 5 W energy-saving bulb.

In this case, only the 5 W energy-saving bulb was switched on, a power of 3.3 W was indicated on the web interface and 4.4 W on the line graph as shown in Fig. 9 and 10. For the case of two resistive loads comprising of 5 W energy-saving bulb and a 60 W non-energy-saving bulb, having a total power of 65 W, 61.5 W was indicated on both the web interface and line graph in Fig. 10 and 11. In the case of two resistive loads comprising of 5 W energy-saving bulb and 60 W incandescent bulb and an inductive load comprising of a 50 W fan, the total power rating was 115 W illustrated in Fig. 12 and 13. It could be observed that a power of 119.8 higher than 115 W was indicated in both the web interface and line graph. In all the cases considered in Fig.9 to 14,

Fig. 9: Web interface showing measured parameters when 5 W energy saving bulb was switched on

Table 1: Experimental Result of the system under resistive and inductive load conditions

Appliances	Power Watts	Power Factor	Voltage V	Energy KWh	Frequency Hz
5W resistive energy saving load.	3.3	1	205.1	0.17	50.1
Resistive Loads (5W energy saving and 60W non-energy saving bulbs.	61.5	1	247.9	0.108	50.1
Resistive Loads (5W energy saving and 60W non-energy saving bulbs and inductive load (50 W fan)	119.8	1	246.5	0.15	49.9

Fig. 10: Line graph showing measured parameters when 5 W energy saving bulb was switched on

Fig. 11: Web interface showing measured parameters when 5 W energy saving bulb and 60 W incandescent bulb were switched on

Fig. 12: Line graph showing measured parameters when 5 W energy saving bulb and 60 W incandescent bulb were switched on

Fig. 13: Web interface showing measured parameters when 5 W energy saving bulb and 60 W incandescent bulb and a 50 W fan were switched on

Fig. 14: Line graph showing measured parameters when 5 W energy saving bulb and 60 W incandescent bulb and a 50 W fan were switched on

This work allows users to be able to know in real time what each of the appliances is consuming by logging in to the web interface from wherever they are. It could also be observed that users can use the facilities in the control panel to remotely shut down high-consumption appliances especially when they are unnecessary to avoid high electricity bills. The system uses IoT technology with Wi-Fi connectivity which is very much available in most mobile phones used by consumers. It can be extended to Internet communication to cover a larger area by using the appropriate router. The device will make users aware of their electricity consumption per appliance and be able to make an informed decisions such as load-shedding for proper electricity management and conservation of funds.

The test performed on different types of equipment such as inductive load, resistive load, energy-saving bulb, and incandescent bulb revealed how different types of loads with different power factors behave when connected to the electrical source. It could be observed that for 5 W, a value of 3.3 W was displayed on the web interface and 4.4 in the line graph compared to a rated power of 5 W. This is an error of -1.7 W and 0.6 W respectively. For resistive loads combining the 5 W non-energy saving bulb and 60 W incandescent bulb, there was a slight reduction in the value of power displayed in the web interface which was 61.5 W compared with the actual rated value of 65 W. This could be a result of losses experienced in the communication medium resulting in attenuation [17] that slightly affected the final value of measurement by an error of -3.5 W. In the case where the resistive loads of 5 W and 60 W were switched on together with the inductive load of 50 W from the standing fan, a total of 119.8 W was observed in the web interface compared with 116 W of the actual calculated value. This slight increase could be due to a power increase as a result of the electromagnetic induction of the coil in the inductive load (McCown, 2023). It could be deduced that despite the attenuation experienced in the communication medium, the inductive load was able to overcome it and produced power that is slightly higher than the rated power of the devices by an error of +3.9 W. With these findings, more research would be carried out to investigate them further. The graphical user interface (GUI) in form of the web can be a valuable tool in research and teaching of electrical engineering and systems automation courses. The developed device could be integrated to be part of a smart metering system that allows customers to be able to manage their load-shedding activities to reduce their electricity bills. It can also be integrated into the micro-grid / smart grid so that users of the renewable energy system can manage loads thereby prolonging the life of their battery which is a major component of the renewable energy system.

5.0 Conclusion

As a means of providing facilities that allow consumers to take charge of their power consumption, a web-based load-shedding device is developed. Tests performed reveal the device's ability to remotely monitor what each of the appliances connected to it is consuming in real time and provide a control panel on a mobile phone or web interface where load-shedding can be achieved. Its integration in the smart meter or renewable energy system for smart grid or microgrid will help to reduce electricity bills as well as make a battery and other renewable energy equipment last longer thereby ensuring effective management of resources. Future work will include extending the coverage of the developed device over the Internet for remote load shedding from any location in the globe and possible integration with a smart meter.

References

- [1] Sushma .S. R, Sowmya P., SeethaLakshmi H. R., and Sowmyashree S. R. (2017), Automated Load Shedding and Notification to the Consumers using GSM, International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing.
- [2] Elinwa, U. K., Ogbaba, J. E. O. & Agboola P. (2021), Cleaner energy in Nigeria residential housing. ScienceDirect: www.editorialmanager.com/rineng/Default.aspx
- [3] Rashidul, K. K., Masud, I. Abu, and Forhad, (2012), Co-Ordinate Load control and Load Shedding Balance by using Microcontroller, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, vol. 3, no 4. 2012.
- [4] Ogidan, O. K., Temikotan, K. O., & Chike, K. C. (2017). Development of an Arduino microcontroller-based automatic load shedding module for teaching and research. 2017 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Electro-Technology for National Development (NIGERCON). <https://doi.org/10.1109/nigercon.2017.8281976>
- [5] Bahar, N., Bharwmick, K., Ullah, A., Das, M., & Faika, T. (2018). Design and Implementation of a Priority-based Load Control System Based on GSM Technology Using Android Application. International Conference on Mechanical Engineering and Renewable Energy 2018.
- [6] Rudrapal, D., Das, S., Pandey, A., & Kar, N. (2011). Automated Load Shedding Period Control System. International Journal on Computer Science and Engineering, 3(5), 1764-1772.
- [7] Rwegasira, D., Dhaou, I. B., Kondoro, A., Kelati, A., Mvungi, N., & Tenhunnen, H. (2019), Load-shedding techniques for microgrids: A comprehensive review. International Journal of Smart Grid and Clean Energy, 341–353. <https://doi.org/10.12720/sgce.8.3.341-353>
- [8] Jack, K. E., Dike, D. O., Obichere, J. K. C., & Olubiwe, M. (2020). The development of an Android Applications Model for the Smart Micro-Grid Power Pool System Monitoring and Control. International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology, 9(3), 3474–3479. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.c5620.029320>
- [9] Okoth, G., Adabara, I., William, M., Mark, E., Mathias, K., & Olusola, F. (2020). Android Platform-based Smart Grid Hybrid Load Control System. International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Science, 04(04), 12–17.
- [10] Patil, U., Titkare, C., Mamidware, A., Kadam, R., & Datey, S. (2020). Automated Load Shedding and Notification to the Consumers using GSM. International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering (IJAREEIE), 9(5), 1042–1046.
- [11] Raza, M. Q., Ali, M., Tareen, N., Rehman, W. U., Khan, A., & Asar, A. U. (2020), Intelligent Load Shedding Using TCP/IP for Smart Grids. Energy and Power Engineering, 04(06), 398–403. <https://doi.org/10.4236/epe.2012.46053>
- [12] Benjamin, E. & Iloh, J.P. & Nwabueze, C. (2019). Addressable Load-shedding System for the Smart Grid. International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology Volume 8. 3928-3934. 10.15680/IJIRSET.2019.0804050.
- [13] Enughwure, A. (2019). Design and Construction of GSM-Based Smart Energy Meter. FUPRE Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research (FJSIR), 3(2), 12-24.

- [14] Sayed, S., Hussain, T., Gastli, A., & Benammar, M. (2019). Design and realization of an open-source and modular smart meter. *Energy Science & Engineering*, 7(4), 1405-1422.
- [15] Aina, F., Osanaiye, O., & Unogwu, S. (2020). A GSM module-based smart electric meter reader. *Acta Electrotechnica et Informatica*, 20(4), 38-45.
- [16] Baloyi, N., Chowdhury, S. D., Mnisi, J., & Mashee, T. (2020, September). Design of GSM Based Energy Meter: A Review. In 2020 6th IEEE International Energy Conference (ENERGYCon) (pp. 836-840). IEEE.
- [17] McCown, C. (2023), What is the effect of load on the attenuation and phase shift across the transmission line, <https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-effect-of-load-on-the-attenuation-and-phase-shift-across-the-transmission-line> [retrieved 20-01-2023].